

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

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RDA for Disciplinary Data

Celebrating A Decade of Data
RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop

Version: August 2023

ABOUT THE WORKSHOP

The community cross-fertilisation workshop, 'RDA for Disciplinary Data', brought chairs and members of RDA Working Groups (WGs) and Interest Groups (IGs) together with members of the wider research data community to share and discuss challenges, solutions, and initiatives associated with managing disciplinary data. This workshop was presented on behalf of [EOSC Future](#) project, an H2020 funded project to develop the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), with [Beth Knazook](#) (Digital Repository of Ireland) as guest co-host. This workshop included findings from the [RDA's Engagement with Underrepresented Communities in EOSC](#). The key findings of the workshop summarised herein will be used to direct the future strategy of the RDA community. Read more about the [community cross-fertilisation workshop series](#) in commemoration of the [RDA's 10th Anniversary](#).

GAPS IN OPEN SCIENCE SUPPORT IN EUROPE

Highlights from RDA's Engagement with Underrepresented Communities

Small data is being left behind

- Small data has a lower individual cost to repeat data collection, which does not incentivise the researcher to take care with the application of standards or documentation for sharing. Many researchers working with small data may choose to regenerate rather than reuse data.
- Small data are often generated via manual processes, particularly in domains where researchers tend to work alone or on very small projects. Data that does not start out digital is difficult to share.

Lack of global access to tools inhibits sharing

- Data sharing has often been successful in situations where communities have been able to build consensus around FAIR-supporting tools, and it is conversely more of a challenge when there are no standardised tools for collecting and managing the data.
- Collaboration is not always possible when technologies are limited by borders.
- Proprietary file formats limit the cross-domain usability of data.

Data sharing is not taught and feels like extra work

- Many established researchers do not know how to do this work because it was not part of a researcher's graduate training or professional development, and in some fields, it still is not required training.

PARTICIPATING GROUPS & WORKSHOP LEADS*

[EOSC Future Project](#)
WP10.2.1 lead: [Beth Knazook](#)

[RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassadors](#)
Featured participants:
[Sofie Meeus](#), Biodiversity
[Marek Cebecauer](#), Materials Sciences
[Helene N. Andreassen](#), Linguistics

[RDA for Disciplines:](#)
[RDA for Disciplines pages](#)
[Disciplinary Info Sheets](#)

[Life Sciences Data Infrastructure IG](#)
Nominated lead: [Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström](#)

See [community group card](#)

[Linguistics IG](#)
Nominated lead: [Helene N. Andreassen](#)

See [community group card](#)

[Biodiversity Data Integration IG](#)
Nominated lead: [Wouter Addink](#)

See [community group card](#)

*Workshop leads collected challenges, solutions and initiatives in preparation for the workshop and explained them during the workshop on behalf of their group.

- In fields where the research is highly varied, researchers struggle to apply Open Science workflows to their specific contexts.
- There is a lot of pressure on the researcher to navigate the ethics of data sharing themselves, making it easier to just avoid sharing altogether.

Funding and evaluation does not reward the whole process

- Data reuse is not as strongly encouraged as data sharing.
- Collaboration promotes good data sharing, but is often limited by access to funds.
- Funders do not generally recognise that it costs the researcher, institution and infrastructures to sustain research outputs.

CHALLENGES IN WORKING WITH DISCIPLINARY DATA

Figuring out where to start

- There are many different stakeholders in a given discipline who require different approaches to engage with Open Science.
- Need to prepare relevant and targeted material not just for each discipline, but the unique sub-disciplines. It is a benefit for every researcher to see examples they can easily connect to their own work.
- It is difficult to catch and retain someone's attention as people have too much to do, and need to focus on the traditional rewards for individual effort.
- RDA's contributions to disciplinary data sharing is scattered and sometimes hard to navigate.

Adapting for different stakeholders

- Research that focuses on minute technicalities leaves little interest or room for sharing.
- Younger researchers are often more open to the 'extra work' of data sharing when they are still training.
- Highly heterogeneous disciplines do not benefit from one-size-fits-all approaches to data sharing.
- It is important not to forget the managers and service providers when engaging in outreach. All the pieces need to be connected to be successful.
- Using and adapting international best practice is important, but there needs to be a two-way communication between the creators and users.

Rewards need to change

- Often few people are concentrating on the types of research that gets traditionally rewarded.
- There needs to be community benefit for sharing to thrive.
- Research assessment has to take into account disciplinary specificities.
- The people doing the work of defining standards, tools, and best practices also need to be recognised in this work.

SOLUTIONS FOR SUPPORTING TARGETED DISCIPLINARY WORK

Connecting to international communities is important

- Standards need to be defined at the international level so that data sharing is not totally siloed, within projects or disciplines. The end goal is still interoperability and reuse.
- Being an Ambassador opens doors for conversations.
- Do not be afraid to test ideas locally and tailor the work to the immediate needs of different audiences.
- Effort needs to be made to sustain the outcomes of resourced work (financial, administrative) that often comes and goes with projects, such as the network of Domain Ambassadors created through European grants.

Support the development of new reward systems

- Advocate for discipline-specific benefits when examining research assessment (e.g. [Evaluation of Research IG](#))

RDA outreach starts locally

- Helping researchers to see examples that apply to their specific situations is one way of adapting RDA work, but there also needs to be continued, institutional-level liaison work with specific RDA activities (e.g. [workshop with SciLifeLab](#)).

ACTIONS FOR THE RDA COMMUNITY

Revive the **Disciplinary Collaboration Frameworks IG** where some discussion of shared challenges could be held.

Support the creation of a **proposed Domain Ambassadors IG** to build on the success of the European-funded ambassadors. Make potential future funding for more global ambassadorships a priority.

Maintain the **RDA for Disciplines web pages** created as part of EOSC Future, as resources for newcomers to RDA and roadmaps for future work in the groups.

Engage with the **RDA Evaluation of Research IG** as an important area of work which needs representation from across the disciplines and subdisciplines.

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INITIATIVES & RESOURCES OF INTEREST

[RDA Disciplinary Pages & Info Sheets](#)

- The disciplinary pages on the RDA website are useful intro pages, but they could also serve as roadmaps for disciplinary development.
- They will be most useful if they're not overcrowded, so that newcomers can make sense of the resources and their purposes/applications.
- It would be great to have a means for anyone to suggest changes (similar to creating an issue in Github), so users can also see when a response has been logged.
- These will only be relevant as long as the community is interested in supporting them.

[RDA Domain Ambassadors](#)

- Profiles, contact info, and a list of key outputs and events from the RDA/EOSC Future and RDA4EOSC Ambassador grantees.
- Birds of a Feather session at RDA Plenary 21 aimed at launching a [Domain Ambassadors IG!](#)
- [Report on RDA Europe 4.0 Ambassador Programme](#)

[Developing a Needs Analysis Survey for Open Scholarship in Linguistics and the Language Sciences](#)

[Data Streams Episode 9: Meet the RDA Life Sciences Infrastructure IG](#)

[Key Aspects of FAIR for Infrastructure Solutions in the Biomolecular Life Sciences](#)

[Six Recommendations for the Implementation of FAIR Practice by the FAIR in Practice Task Force of the European Open Science Cloud FAIR Working Group](#)

[Disciplinary Collaboration Framework IG](#) (historical group)

WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

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For more information about the RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop series, please contact:

- Connie Clare, Community Development Manager (connie.clare@rda-foundation.org);
- Kathryn Barker, Community Development manager Australasia (kathryn.barker@ardc.edu.au)

To become a member of the RDA, register [here](#).